

FUNCTIONALIZATION OF GLASS BY SOL-GEL LAYERS

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ABSTRACT

The demands for flat glass are still at high-level, because this glass is exposed to the effect of surrounding environment. Fulfilment of these demands is commonly carried out by „functionalization“. Functionalization is used for preparation of anti-reflective and reflective glass and in some cases, colour as well as self-cleaning glass can be involved there.

The present study deals with determination of the sol composition effect on antireflection and hydrophobicity of inorganic-organic films in “tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) - triethoxy(octyl)silane (OTES) - distilled water - nitric acid - isopropyl alcohol” system. The fifteen sols were prepared where the molar ratio (K) of the $(OTES)/((OTES)+(TEOS))$ varied from 0 to 0.5 and molar ratio (R) of the $(H_2O)/((OTES)+(TEOS))$ varied from 2 to 6. For determination of “sol composition - film properties” relation, the corrected Akaike information criterion was used for model selection approach.

On the basis of selected models, the dependences of refractive index and hydrophobicity on sol composition were determined. Determined dependences were discussed from the aspect of possible deposition application on flat glass.

Keywords: Sol-gel, Films, Glass, Functionalization

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